

Research Symposium: The Politics of Time

Introduction

Diana B. Greenwald and Rola El-Husseini

Diana B. Greenwald is an associate professor in the Department of Political Science at City College of New York.

Rola El-Husseini is an associate professor in the Department of Political Science at Lund University, Sweden.

While the passage of time may be one of the few truly exogenous variables to shape our lives and interactions, it is woven into our identities, our experiences, and our political institutions in so many ways that it is often hard, if not impossible, to isolate its effects. In designing a symposium on the “politics of time” in the MENA region, we sought to cast a wide net, inviting scholars who have thought about time from diverse methodological and regional perspectives. We invited authors to reflect on the following overarching question: “How does the passage of time influence individuals’ political experiences, behavior, and engagement with political processes and institutions in your country (or countries) of expertise?” We asked our contributors to draw on their own areas of expertise to structure their interventions. Possible temporal themes, we offered, might include the political significance of particular historical events or “shocks”, the ways that age and the life course might shape individual-level

political experiences, and the political salience (or lack thereof) of generational membership.

Selin Bengi Gümrükçü is our only contributor to focus exclusively on the long-run effects of a particular historical period. Gümrükçü explores the enduring legacies of the unrest in Turkey during the 1970s and the subsequent 1980 military coup. She contends that right-wing political mobilization from this time – and its associated historical narratives and brand of nationalism – is pivotal in explaining the decline of Turkey’s democracy in more recent years.

Gümrükçü’s treatment of how narratives of the past play into public memory in Turkey is a theme that is echoed in other pieces in this symposium. For example, Sarah Anne Rennick and Tamirace Fakhoury both elucidate how politicians and regimes attempt to mold time to their own ends, whether by control-

ling the pacing of policy or by leveraging particular narratives of the country's past, present, or future. These pieces draw our attention to the concept of "chronopolitics," a term used for analyzing the organization, regulation, and strategic use of time as a tool of authority and legitimacy (see Esposito and Becker 2023). The concept questions the notion of time as an objective, linear, or universal constant, instead presenting it as a dimension that is shaped by—and shapes—social and political power dynamics. Rennick uses chronopolitics to unpack how Kais Saied's restoration of authoritarianism in Tunisia relies on manipulation of the temporal rhythm of politics, in addition to the propagation of specific imaginaries of the country's past, present, and future. This form of rule appears to have shaped how young people view their own futures and propensity for political engagement. Fakhoury uses post-civil war Lebanon as a case to reveal how governments may alternate between slow and fast policy time, both within and across policy sectors. These tactics can serve to "normalize crisis", shift responsibility or blame, and govern access to rights, among other things. Both pieces speak to how temporal elements are intentionally leveraged, or even weaponized, as instruments of control. Far from being incidental effects of bureaucratic delays or policy failures, time and temporality operate as deliberate and tactical means of governing (Stierl 2023).

Three additional contributions approach the issue of time differently and tackle questions related to the experiences and perspectives of particular cohorts, or generations. These scholars both identify and interrogate the existence of political generations, or groups shaped by critical events or similar social, economic, or political contexts at a particular stage of their life course. Following the ap-

proach of Mannheim ([1928] 1952), research often emphasizes the importance of events and experiences during one's "formative", or "impressionable", years—roughly adolescence to early adulthood (Stoker 2014, 378).

Adam Almqvist shines a light on how economic insecurity and narrowing channels of opportunity have contributed to intergenerational injustice in Jordan. When it comes to framing shared generational experiences, Almqvist highlights how the process of meaning-making is contested and shaped by cultural critics, representatives of the monarchy, and the everyday narratives of today's youth.

Ameni Mehrez asks whether the generation that came of age during the Arab Spring expresses significantly different attitudes toward democracy when compared to an older, comparison cohort. Using generalized additive models to address the age-period-cohort collinearity problem, she finds no evidence of cohort-specific effects or trends. Both Mehrez and David Patel urge us to think carefully about the assumptions we bring to our theories and analysis of the political effects of time. Patel argues that quantitative age-period-cohort (APC) research provides a helpful conceptual framework for more qualitative-based work that seeks to ascertain generational effects. On the other hand, qualitatively informed theories of the causal processes associated with time-based effects might inform quantitative analyses, too.

Time is a fundamental yet elusive force in politics, shaping identities, institutions, and power dynamics in ways that are deeply intertwined with social and historical contexts. This symposium has explored the "politics of time" in the MENA region through diverse lenses, revealing how temporal narratives,

generational experiences, and strategic chronopolitics influence political behavior and governance.

Collectively, these pieces underscore that time is not merely a neutral backdrop but an active dimension of political contestation. By bringing these perspectives together, this symposium advances our understanding of how time, in all its complexity, structures power and resistance in the MENA region and beyond. ♦

References

Esposito, Fernando and Tobias Becker. 2023. "The Time of Politics, The Politics of Time, and Politicized Time: An Introduction to Chronopolitics.." *History and Theory* 62(4): 3-23.

Mannheim, Karl. [1928] 1952. "The Problem of Generations." In *Essays on the Sociology of Knowledge*. London: Routledge: 276-322.

Stierl, Maurice. 2023. "Rebel spirits at sea: Disrupting EUrope's weaponizing of time in maritime migration governance." *Security Dialogue* 54(4): 356-373.

Stoker, Laura. 2014. "Reflections on the Study of Generations in Politics." *The Forum* 12(3): 377-396.